

AM1 and DFT calculation of dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophanes

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Abstract : Semiempirical molecular orbital treatment at the level of AM1 (RHF) and single point DFT level calculations has been performed on dicyano (-CN) derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophanes (*para*-cyclophane derivatives) at different positions [the bridge positions and phane-deck(s)]. All the isomeric structures studied here found are stable and endothermic as well. The effect of -CN group on the stability of the *para*-cyclophane derivatives is found. The frontier molecular orbital energies are calculated and the energy gap between HOMO and LUMO is reported.

Keywords : Cyclophanes, cyanocyclophanes, AM1 calculations, DFT calculations.

The cyclophane era is generally regarded as having begun with Brown and Farthing in 1949¹. The interest of Brown and Farthing arose out of the experiments of Szwarc² who showed, pyrolysis of *p*-xylene can give a linear polymer from which di-*p*-xylylene or [2₂]-paracyclophane can be isolated.

[2₂]-paracyclophane

Simultaneously and independently, Cram and Steinberg³ designed and prepared di-*p*-xylylene via intramolecular Wurtz coupling of 1,2-bis(4-bromoethylphenyl)-ethane. Cyclophane is a ring system in which more than two atoms of an aromatic ring are incorporated into a larger ring system. When two or more aromatic rings are stacked face to face, some transannular interaction is expected between their π -electronic systems. Such an interaction is observed in studies on many double-layered compounds, such as [2₂]-paracyclophanes⁴. Un-

usual molecular strain brought about by π -electron repulsion when the aromatic rings are closely fixed within van der Waals distance by virtue of short methylene bridges. Because of these structural features anomalous physical and chemical behaviour has been observed for the layered compounds^{5,6}. It is revealed that π -electrons systems of two arene decks combine to give a new π -system whose HOMO and LUMO generally possess different energies compared to the corresponding arene system itself⁷. Such type of result is due to 'through-space' and 'through-bond' interactions⁸⁻¹⁰ generally occur in [2_{*n*}] type arenophanes and sometimes in [3_{*n*}] types. Chemistry of cyclophanes finds its potential applications in the field of coordination chemistry, catalysis¹¹⁻¹⁴ and to explain various properties theoretical investigations were made as well¹⁵⁻¹⁹. In the present work, a number of isomeric diamino and dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophanes have been investigated for semiempirical and DFT quantum chemical study. To the best of our knowledge this is the first report of DFT and AM1 calculation on dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophanes.

Method :

In this present study, the geometry optimizations of all the derivatives leading to energy minima have been obtained by using AM1 self-consistent fields molecular orbital (SCF-MO)²⁰ method at the restricted Hartree-Fock (RHF) level²¹. The optimized structures of different derivatives were obtained by the application of the Steepest-Descent method followed by conjugate gradient methods, Fletcher-Reeves and Polak-Ribiere consecutively.

[Convergence limit : 4.18×10^{-4} kJ mol⁻¹ (0.0001 kcal mol⁻¹), RMS gradient : 4.18×10^7 kJ mol⁻¹ (0.01 kcal mol⁻¹)]

Single point DFT calculation with exchange/correlation B3LYP method were done on the final AM1 optimized structures of the dicyclo derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophanes. All the computations were performed using the Hyperchem (7.5) software package.

Results and discussion

In the present treatise a number of isomeric dicyano [2₂](1,4)-cyclophanes having cyano groups at different positions of the phane bridges. Only a limited number of isomers are considered for quantum chemical analysis and the structures are given in Fig. 1. Structure **1a**, **1b** and **1c** have cyano groups at different bridge carbons; compounds **1d**, **1e** and **1f** possess cyano groups at different positions of the same phane-deck and structures **1g**, **1h**, **1i** and **1j** have the cyano groups at different phane decks.

Stability of dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophanes :

Optimized energies, obtained from semiempirical AM1 method, of isomeric [2₂](1,4)-cyclophane having different type of structures (**1a-j**) are listed in Table 1. Single point energy calculated from DFT method (with 6-31G basis set) on AM1 optimized structures are listed in Table 2. It has been observed that the optimized energy calculated from DFT method (6-31G basis set) showed little improvement over the AM1 optimized energy. Our procedure is rather cost effective as far as the computational time is concerned. Energies listed in Tables 1 and 2 are negative in magnitude in all cases (**1a-j**) indicating their stability. Heat of formation data (Table 1) for the compounds studied (**1a-j**) points to the fact that all the compounds are endothermic in nature. The degree of endothermic character is in the order of **1a** > **1b** > **1c** > **1e** > **1h** = **1f** > **1d** > **1i** > **1j** = **1g**. As far as the stability, in terms of energy, is concerned the similar trend is followed. The above order indicates that the bridge substituted dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophanes are less favoured than that of ring substituted isomers. It is quite obvious from the resonance consideration that the ring-substituted dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophane involve in conjugation with the benzene ring and thus shows extra stability compared to the bridge substituted dicyano derivatives. The AM1 (RHF) optimized structures of compounds **1a-j** are given in Fig. 1. In order to explain the stability of the structures, all the

Fig. 1. The optimized geometrical structures of considered dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophanes (**1a-j**).

compounds (**1a-j**) are divided into three subsets. In set-I compounds (**1a**, **1b** and **1c**) the -CN groups are in different bridge positions. The -CN groups are in the different positions of the same benzene ring in set-II (compounds **1d**, **1e** and **1f**). In set-III (**1g**, **1h**, **1i** and **1j**) two -CN

Table 1. Calculated energies (AM1) for the structures considered for dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophane (**1a-j**)

Structure	Total energy	Binding energy	Electronic energy	Core-Core repulsion	Heats of formation
1a	-280604	-16321	-2039641	1759036	545
1b	-280610	-16327	-2025909	1745299	540
1c	-280610	-16327	-2024421	1743811	539
1d	-280628	-16345	-2051740	1771112	522
1e	-280622	-16339	-2057287	1776665	528
1f	-280628	-16345	-2049242	1768613	521
1g	-280633	-16350	-2047851	1767218	517
1h	-280629	-16346	-2053541	1772912	521
1i	-280632	-16349	-2051732	1771100	518
1j	-280633	-16350	-2046628	1765995	517

All the energies are in kJ mol⁻¹.

Isolated atomic energy for all the structures is 264460 kJ mol⁻¹.

Table 2. Calculated energies (AM1) for the structures considered for dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophane (**1a-j**)

Structure	Total energy	Electronic energy	Nuclear repulsion energy
1a	-2108379	2098324	3908377
1b	-2108399	2098518	3874184
1c	-2108401	2098509	3870772
1d	-2108444	2098475	3936666
1e	-2108436	2098465	3951100
1f	-2108446	2098470	3930710
1g	-2108452	2098484	3927466
1h	-2108438	2098502	3941239
1i	-2108449	2098482	3936514
1j	-2108453	2098482	3924425

All the energies are in kJ mol⁻¹.

groups are in the different positions of the benzene rings present.

Taking into account the structure **1a**, **1b** and **1c** where the bridge positions are substituted, the DFT calculated total energy data (Table 2) indicate the stability order as **1c** > **1b** > **1a**. As the -CN groups move apart maximum in **1c** (Fig. **1c**), the compound **1c** becomes most stable among the three. The structures become less endothermic similarly.

When structure **1d**, **1e** and **1f** is considered where the cyanide groups reside in the "same phane-deck", the 1,4 dicyano substituted derivative becomes most stable. Between 1,2 (Fig. **1c**) and 1,3 (Fig. **1d**) dicyano derivatives the 1,3 dicyano substituted compound becomes more stable. Therefore the stability order becomes **1f** > **1d** >

1e which is not very much reflected in the results of AM1 calculation but becomes clear from the energy terms obtained from the more precise DFT approach. As far as the directional nature of the cyano group is concerned both 2 and 4 position has the similar effect. But the cyano group being *meta* directing in nature, the 1,3 dicyano derivative (Fig. **1d**) gets extra stability than that of 1,2 and 1,4 dicyano substituted derivative. Thus we believe, the steric factors play the major role for the stability of these dicyano derivatives. From the optimized structures it is obvious that 1,2 dicyano derivative will show more 'through space' interaction between the cyano group and the 1,4 derivative will show the least. Therefore the stability order is like **1f** > **1d** > **1c**.

In the structures where the cyano groups are in 'different phane-decks' four different structures are possible (**1g**, **1h**, **1i** and **1j**). The AM1 calculated energy terms suggest the stability order of **1j** ≈ **1g** > **1i** > **1h** but DFT calculations show the stabilities of order **1j** > **1g** > **1i** > **1h**. This order of stability can be explained in terms of steric interaction of the two -CN groups and it is quiet obvious that in the most stable structure (**1j**) the two -CN groups reside maximum apart to minimize energy.

Considering stabilities of all the structure, the calculated data given in Tables 1 and 2 indicates the fact that when the two cyano groups are in different decks most stable structures are obtained. The position of the substituents plays a vital role for stability. That very structure gains maximum stability (**1j**) where two cyanide groups are in different decks and are in maximum distance. Structure **1g** has comparable stability. Compound **1i** is also stable. However the stability of compound **1f** is comparable to structure **1d**. The heat of formation data for the structure (**1a-j**) is comparable.

The above discussion indicate that in the range of dicyano derivatives of [2₂](1,4)-cyclophane isomers, it is feasible to find out the iso- or almost the iso- energetic structure which could be synthesized via different routes. The stability data for various structures may (having different physical and chemical properties) would be able to give a proper guideline to ease of synthesis.

The frontier molecular orbital energies :

In Table 3, the energies of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) for the compounds (**1a-j**) are listed. The energy gap between HOMO and LUMO i.e. the inter frontier molecular orbital energy gap (ΔE) is also given in the same table.

Table 3. Frontier orbital energies and the inter frontier molecular orbital energy gap (ΔE) of the considered structures

Structure	HOMO	LUMO	ΔE
1a	-14 8831	-0 2787	14.6044
1b	-14 9092	-0.3522	14.5570
1c	-14.9412	-0.3315	14.6097
1d	-14 8617	-1.1621	13 6996
1e	-14.8450	-1.2797	13.5653
1f	-14.8526	-1.6063	13.2463
1g	-15.0787	-0 8485	14.2302
1h	-15.0321	-0.8703	14.1618
1i	-15.0642	-0.8175	14.2467
1j	-15 0778	-0.9071	14.1707

All the energies are in 10^{-19} J

At first we consider the first three compounds (1a, 1b and 1c). In this set compound 1c has the lowest lying HOMO orbital as the -CN groups are maximum apart from each other. Compound 1a possess the highest lying HOMO orbitals where the two -CN groups are in the bridge carbon.

Fig. 2 (contd)

Fig. 2 (contd.)

Fig. 2. The HOMO and LUMO of compounds (1a-j).

For compound **1d**, **1e** and **1f** where the cyanide groups reside at the "same phane deck", the increasing order of energies are like $1d < 1f < 1e$ and $1f < 1e < 1d$ for HOMO and LUMO respectively.

The third set of compounds (**1g**, **1h**, **1i** and **1j**) has the deeper line HOMO energies in comparison to the other compounds. Here the increasing order of energies of HOMO and LUMO are $1g < 1j < 1i < 1h$ and $1j < 1h < 1g < 1i$ respectively. Fig. 2 shows the HOMO and LUMO for the compounds (1a-j) studied. The ΔE values for compounds **1d**, **1e** and **1f** are smaller in comparison to the other. The first set of compounds (**1a**, **1b** and **1c**) possesses the highest ΔE values.

Conclusion :

The present treatise on the single point DFT calculation with exchange/correlation B3LYP method on the AM1 (RHF) level optimized structures of different dicyano derivatives [2_2](1,4)-cyclophanes reveal that the dicyano derivatives of paracyclophanes are endothermic but stable compounds. In general for these types of compounds, the closer the -CN groups, the compound becomes less stable. The stabilities are explained quite nicely from the DFT level calculated energy data. The heats of formation data of the compounds studied do not differ much from each other [within the limitation of AM1 (RHF)]. This is probably due to transmission of mesomeric and inductive ef-

fect of -CN groups through - space as effective as through bonds.

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